

GNSS

Post-processing

(NMEA file correction and georeferencing)

Revision history

Date	Author	Description of change
8/1/2021	António Ferreira	First version

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Preparation step.....	4
3. File consistency check and correction.....	4
3.1. Removal of corrupted records.....	5
3.2. Ensure chronological consistency.....	5
4. Position interpolation.....	6
5. Data georeferencing.....	7

1. Introduction

This document describes the post-processing of the SAIL data in order to generate the final GNSS files and georeference the data acquired from the other sensors. The procedure is composed of four steps:

- 1 Preparation step (unpacking and building the folder tree)
- 2 File consistency check and correction
- 3 Position interpolation
- 4 Data georeferencing

2. Preparation step

The data is originally stored in the compress .tgz format, so the first step is to decompress all the data manually. The decompressed data should be placed inside folder *extraidos*. Folder *extraidos* should be placed inside the same folder where the compressed files are stored.

The file tree should look like:

```

GPS                                     (parent folder containing the compressed files)
|— 20200105.tgz                       (compressed file for day 5 of January of 2020)
|— 20200106.tgz                       (compressed file for day 6 of January of 2020)
.
.
.
├── extraidos                          (stores all uncompressed files)
│   ├── 20200105                       (all GNSS log files for day (NMEA+RAW))
│   │   └──
│   └── 20200106
│       .
│       .
│       .

```

3. File consistency check and correction

The original log files suffer from some inconsistencies, which occur more frequently during the first days of mission. Those inconsistencies can be of two types:

- ▮ **Corrupted records** - entries in the log file that do not comply with the specified string format, and can be identified individually through a checksum analysis.
- ▮ **Chronological inconsistency** - Measurements acquired during hour X, stored on files corresponding to a different hour Y. Also, due to the same error, the last measurements of a given day may be stored in files from the following day.

3.1. Removal of corrupted records

Since this problem was soon detected and corrected, it only affects some of the first files of the expedition. Those files need to be individually identified and corrected using the program **clean_corrupted.c**. As an argument, the user should specify the path of the file to be analysed. A new file, in the same folder, named after the original file plus the suffix *_corrected* is created. In the new file, all lines should now start with the characters '#' or '\$'. Hopefully, the new file is consistent and can be used to replace the original.

Usage example: Invoke program `clean_corrupted` to correct file stored in
`/run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/20200105/GPS1_NMEA_20200105_11`

```
# Step 1 - Compile the program
$ gcc clean_corrupted.c -o clean
```

```
# Step 2 - Execute the program
./clean
/run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/20200105/GPS1_NMEA_20200105_11
```

```
#Step 3 - Visually inspect file
/run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/20200105/GPS1_NMEA_20200105_11_co
rrected
```

```
#Step 4 - If the new file is consistent, use it to replace the original file
```

3.2. Ensure chronological consistency

This step is used to produce the final NMEA files, where measurements are organized into hourly files. Also, the consistency of each NMEA sentence is verified through a checksum analysis. The user should run the program `generate_final_nmea_files.c` and supply the path to the folder containing the daily folders. The program automatically corrects all NMEA files recorded during the expedition.

Usage example: To correct all NMEA files inside folder `/run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/`

```
#Step 1 - Edit file generate_final_nmea_files.h to adjust the starting date of the first file to be processed. Change the following three constants:
```

```
#define INIT_DAY 10
#define INIT_MONTH 3
#define INIT_YEAR 2020
```

```
# Step 2 - Compile the program
```

```
$ gcc generate_final_nmea_files.c -o generate_final
```

```
# Step 3 - Execute the program
```

```
./generate_final /run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/
```

#Step 4 - A new folder /run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/PostProcessed holds the final NMEA files.

Debug: In case the program issues any checksum errors for a given file, the clean_corrupted.c program should be run for that particular file.

4. Position interpolation

During the first expedition some data gaps were detected:

9 of January:

- ▮ Gap of 700 seconds - from 09:27:52 to 09:39:53
- ▮ Gap of 30 seconds - from 09:40:37 to 09:41:08

10 and 11 of January several data losses due to maintenance actions at Tenerife's Harbor

16 of January:

- ▮ Gap of 4000 seconds - from 12:45:59 to 13:52:12
- ▮ Gap of 410 seconds - from 15:55:08 to 16:01:58
- ▮ Gap of 153 seconds - from 16:19:22 to 16:21:55

18 of January:

- ▮ Gap of 1370 seconds - from 19:46:15 to 20:09:05

20 of January (Paria's Harbor):

- ▮ Gap of 151 seconds - from 15:19:39 to 15:22:10

24 January:

- ▮ Gap of 652 seconds - from 12:57:17 to 13:08:10

31 January:

- ▮ Gap of 1497 seconds - from 15:33:12 to 15:58:09

11, 12 and 13 of February at the Rio de Janeiro's Harbor:

- ▮ Several data gaps, including a 10 hour gap

17 February:

- ▮ Gap of 575 seconds - from 18:45:19 to 18:54:54
- ▮ Gap of 15 seconds - from 18:56:32 to 18:56:33
- ▮ Gap of 151 seconds - from 18:58:13 to 19:00:44

24 February Montevideo's Harbor:

- ▮ Gap of 12533 seconds - from 14:00 to 17:00

8 and 9 of March: System failure

4, 5, 6 of April - Data acquisition fails for 3 days

23 to 28 of April - Several data acquisition fails while at Mindelo's Harbor

7 of May:

- ▮ Gap of 127 seconds - from 11:00:39 to 11:02:46

The interpolation.c program analyses all files from a given GNSS antenna to produce a continuous trajectory, filling the data gap periods with straight line trajectories.

Usage example:

#Step 1 - Edit file *interpolate.h* to adjust the period of interest. Change the following six constants:

```
#define INIT_DAY 5
#define INIT_MONTH 1
#define INIT_YEAR 2020

#define FINAL_DAY 15
#define FINAL_MONTH 6
#define FINAL_YEAR 2020
```

Step 2 - Compile the program

```
$ gcc interpolate.c -o interpolate -lm
```

Step 3 - Execute the program

```
./interpolate /run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/PostProcessed
```

#Step 4 - Several files (one for each day) are created inside folder

```
/run/media/sail_SD/sail1/GPS/extraidos/PostProcessed
```

5. Data georeferencing

Finally, measurements from the other sensors are georeferenced, based on the interpolated position files, using programs *georeference.c*. Program *georeference_cic.c* should be used for the CIC.

Usage example: georeference the data collected by the Electric Field 1, stored in folder
/run/media/sail_SD/SAIL_SD_E1

```
./g2
/run/media/aferreira/d381fe8f-7f08-4be8-af06-2e7f2c19c003/sail_merged/
SAIL_SD_E1/ E1 .txt
```

#Step 1 - Edit file *georeference.h* to adjust the period of interest. Change the following six constants:

```
#define INIT_DAY 5
#define INIT_MONTH 1
#define INIT_YEAR 2020

#define FINAL_DAY 15
#define FINAL_MONTH 6
#define FINAL_YEAR 2020
```

Step 2 - Compile the programs

```
$ gcc georeference.c -o georeference
$ gcc georeference_cic.c -o georeference_cic
```

Step 3 - Execute the program

```
./georeference /run/media/sail_SD/SAIL_SD_E1/ E1 .txt
```

The program requires 3 arguments:

- 1 path to the folder storing the data to georeference
- 2 ID of the corresponding sensor:

Sensor	Sensor ID
Electric field 1	E1
Electric field 2	E2
Gamma	GA
Visibility	VI
Solar radiance	SL
Towfish' CTD	CTD

- 3 file suffix

#Step 4 - Georeferenced files are placed inside a new folder

```
/run/media/sail_SD/SAIL_SD_E1_georreferenced/
```